

Self Efficacy and Spiritual Values as Predictors of Life Satisfaction among School Teachers

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ABSTRACT

The present investigation was intended to ascertain the role of self efficacy and spiritual values on life satisfaction among school teachers. Sample consisted of 120 school teachers from different districts of Uttar Pradesh, India. They were assessed by Teacher's Self Efficacy scale (Ansari M., Khan S.A. and Khan S.M., 2017), Spiritual Values Scale (Husain A., Zehra S. and Jahan M., 2015) and Life Satisfaction Scale (Diener, Emmons, Larsen, and Griffen, 1985). Pearson product moment correlation was applied to study the relationship among self efficacy, spiritual values and life satisfaction, whereas it was found that these all variables are positively and significantly correlated with each other. Before proceeding to regression analysis robustness of the data was examined and found appropriate to go ahead. The multiple linear (stepwise) regression was administered to study the contribution of teacher's self efficacy and spiritual values on life satisfaction, result shows that teacher's self efficacy and spiritual values are accounted for a significant amount of variance in life satisfaction of school teachers.

Keywords: *Self efficacy, Spiritual Values and Life satisfaction and School teachers*

There are several resources in the world, in which human resource playing very important role in any organization. Teachers are one of them who transfer their knowledge and values in the pupils. They are the model of society in whom people have faith, ultimately they needs to strengthen dedication towards the task. Therefore, it is a general consensus that teacher should have high efficacy, spiritual values and life satisfaction. Hence, taking all these things into consideration the mentioned variables are drawn to study among school teachers.

Definition and Characteristics of Self Efficacy

As Ormrod (2006) define "*self-efficacy is the extent or strength of one's belief in one's own ability to complete tasks and reach goals.*" On the other hand Luszczynska & Schwarzer (2005) describe that "*self-efficacy affects every area of human endeavor. By determining the beliefs a person holds regarding his or her power to affect situations, it strongly influences*

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both the power a person actually has to face challenges competently and the choices a person is most likely to make. These effects are particularly apparent, and compelling, with regard to behaviors affecting health.”

Self-efficacy is self-perception of an individual's capability which becomes instrumental when he pursue to the goals and the control which he can exercise over his environments. Albert Bandura (1977a) focused on human behavior and motivation in which he described that self-efficacy as individuals believes about their own capabilities which guide the person that what actually they are capable of accomplishing. It is the belief which they hold about their capabilities which help in determining what a person can do with knowledge and skills which he possesses.

Spiritual Values

Husain, Zehra and Jahan M. (2015), describe that, “the spiritual/human values are the fundamental roots of a healthy, vibrant, viable organization –of healthy, vibrant, and viable individuals.” For example:

1. Commitment promotes the state or quality of being dedicated to a cause, activity, etc.
2. Courage fosters the ability to do something that frightens one; bravery.
3. Creativity fosters the use of imagination or original ideas to create something; inventiveness.
4. Dedication fosters the quality of being dedicated or committed to a task or purpose.
5. Discipline fosters the practice of training people to obey rules or a code of behaviour.
6. Justice fosters the quality of being just; fairness: in the interest of justice, we should treat everyone the same.
7. Knowledge promotes facts, information, and skills acquired through experience or education; the theoretical or practical understanding of a subject.
8. Responsibility encourages the state or fact of having a duty to deal with something or of having control over someone.
9. Sense of duty cultivates a motivating awareness of ethical responsibility
10. Wisdom promotes the quality of having experience, knowledge, and good judgment; the quality of being wise.
11. Compassion fosters sympathetic pity and concern for the sufferings or misfortunes of others.
12. Connectedness cultivates the state or quality of being connected.
13. Empathy encourages the ability to understand and share the feelings of another.

Spiritual values imply that they are something that human beings aspire and hopefully someday achieve. We are well aware that most people see human nature as anything but spiritual – they typically see it as limited, imperfect, and so on. However, we know that we are spiritual beings first and foremost and that “to be human is to be spiritual.” So, by calling these spiritual values or “human values,” it reminds us that they are inbuilt in our nature.

There are three principles of it:

1. Their spiritual essence, based on the principle that Divinity resides in all of creation.

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2. Their cross-cultural expressions, which we find in all societies though there may be variations and different emphasis from culture to culture.
3. Their individual (personal) expressions, which reflect the attitudes and motivations beneath our unique personalities and behaviour.

Spiritual values are also known as human values and are the fundamental roots of a healthy, energetic, and practical work career. The values of truth, righteousness, peace, love non-violence, commitment, courage, creativity, dedication, discipline, justice, knowledge, responsibilities, sense of duty, wisdom, compassion, connectedness and empathy are found in all major spiritual paths.

Life Satisfaction

Life satisfaction, in general, represents personal satisfaction about his/her own life (Telman and Ünsal 2004).

Life satisfaction shows the result of comparison of personal expectations and reality. When we use the term “life satisfaction”, we understand a general satisfaction, not about a specific event (Ozdevecio ğlu and Aktas 2007).

According to Keng, Ah Kau; Kwon Jung; Tan Soo Jiuan; Jochen Wirtz (2000), “The overall life satisfaction comes from inside of an individual based on the individual's personal values and what he or she holds important. For some it is family, for others it is love, and for others it is money or other material items; it varies from one person to another. Economic materialism can be considered a value. Previous research found that materialistic individuals were predominantly male, and that materialistic people also reported a lower life satisfaction level than their non-materialistic counterparts.”

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Review of related literature is an important pre-requisite for actual planning and carrying out of any research work. The present section represents a brief review of the researches done in the area related to the present investigation.

Teachers spend more time for the teaching of their students and behave in a more responsible and sincere manner particularly for the students with low achiever. Life satisfaction is the combination of the processes of patterns of life and life standards of individuals. Variables such as economic condition, professional status, and conditions of the environment they work and expectation levels are the factors affecting life satisfaction of teachers (Lewandowski, 2005). As a result, the way teachers perceive job satisfaction and occupational stress affect their life satisfaction (Avşarođlu S., Deniz M. E. & Kahraman A., 2005).

According to Bandura's (1977a, 1986) social cognitive theory, individual possess a self-system which enables them to exercise a measure of control over their thoughts, feelings, motivation and actions. The self-system encompasses one's cognitive and affective structure

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that provides a reference mechanism of perceiving, regulating and evaluating behavior that results from between the system and the environmental sources of influence. Every individual estimates his ability to get things done, it may be an important element of a person's self-concept, which is a constellation of beliefs and experiences about his/her ability to deal effectively with the tasks and accomplish what needs to be done. Bandura (1977b) suggested that self-efficacy is an important component of self-concept. He further suggested that low self-efficacy lead to negative mood, pessimism, stress, tension and psychological distress.

According to Medenick (1982) personal efficacy refers to a belief or expectation that one can successfully bring about change, people with expectation are more likely to take risks, set more difficult goals, persist longer at chosen activities and be more involved in what they are doing. Deaux (1976) stated that the people having high efficacy attribute success to ability or high effort and failure to lack of effort in some instances to external factors such individuals expect to be successful in what they do and other expect them to be successful.

Brouwers and Tomic (2000) found that self-efficacy beliefs were significantly and negatively related to depersonalization and emotional exhaustion, and significantly and positively related to personal accomplishment.

Hampton (2000) found that "self efficacy and health status were positively and significantly correlated with life satisfaction."

Viel-Ruma et al. (2010) studied self efficacy beliefs of special educators. In order to examine the relationship between reported levels of teacher self efficacy, collective efficacy, and satisfaction in special educators, teachers in one school district completed three surveys measuring these constructs. The results indicated that teacher self efficacy had a direct effect on satisfaction.

Telef (2011) investigated the relationship between the self-efficacy, job satisfactions, life satisfactions and burnout of teachers. The sample consists of both male and female teachers. Results indicated that self-efficacy (efficacy for student's engagement, efficacy for instructional strategies, and the efficacy for class management) had statistically significant positive relationship with teacher's job and life satisfactions, and has a negative relationship with their burnout.

Spiritual values of the employees are the fundamental roots of a healthy and vibrant organization. By exploring the employees' spiritual values, the integrated wholeness can bring forth tremendous strength in the work life, which leads them to life satisfaction.

Value fosters high quality work which increasingly recognizes that values help us to motivate in our work and give us a feeling of satisfaction. As a result, organizations/schools now focus on the development of values among employees/teachers in order to develop their interests in work/teaching and intellectual abilities. In a career context, values might include work security and satisfaction, a regular income and a fixed pattern of responsibilities, and autonomy. An

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employee's spiritual values at work may be affected by such factors as socioeconomic status, gender, ethnicity, cultural context, and the more likely he finds his career choice satisfying. As the career goes on, the satisfaction or dissatisfaction with the job an employee feel may help to evaluate himself including his values (Husain A., Zehra S. and Jahan M., 2015).

An employee's values can determine how and where he applies his skills. For example, an employee may be good in dealing with people, but his values are likely to determine whether he use that skill in sales, teaching or in counseling. We use values to assign positive and negative properties to different careers and lifestyles, and make decisions on that basis. Within the same profession (e.g. teaching, law, management) there will always be a variety of areas with different aims, working environments, attitudes to their employees and potential for progression (Husain A., Zehra S. and Jahan M., 2015).

Spiritual beliefs are typically related to spiritual values. For example, the identity of a person or group is shaped by spiritual values, beliefs, and affiliation. Spiritual values come from a common spiritual foundation, they are indivisible whole. Values cannot exist apart from the others. Spiritual values are often passed on to future generations. There are many reasons as to why people are drawn to a religious or spiritual way of life. Many people develop spiritual values from the prophets, guidance and teachings of sacred books and thinkers because they feel satisfaction with these practices/characteristics (Husain A., Zehra S. and Jahan M., 2015).

Spiritual values have eternal qualities, arising from deep-seated inner connectedness to the divine of spiritual dimension of human experience. Spiritual values imply that they are something that human beings need to cultivate for the satisfaction. We are well aware that most people judge human nature in terms of values.

Objectives

- To study the relationship between self efficacy, spiritual values and life satisfaction among school teachers.
- To assess the role of self efficacy and spiritual values on life satisfaction among school teachers.

Hypotheses

- There is positive and significant relationship between self efficacy, spiritual values and life satisfaction among school teachers.
- There is positive and significant contribution of self efficacy on life satisfaction among school teachers.
- There is positive and significant contribution of spiritual values on life satisfaction among school teachers.

METHODOLOGY

Sample

Participants: Sample of the study consisted of 120 school teachers; their age range was 24 to 620. They were selected by probability (cluster) sampling technique from the different

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schools, where they were already clustered in pre-existing groups and the researcher randomly selected the group.

Tools

1. Teacher's Self Efficacy Scale

The Teacher's Self Efficacy Scale (Ansari M., Khan S.A. and Khan S.M., 2017), consisted of 23 items, these items are distributed in six (6) constructs/dimensions i.e. Restraint, outgoing/Participating, Evolving, Versatile, High Expectations and Constructive. This is a Likert type scale based on six points as Strongly Disagree (1), Disagree (2), Somewhat Disagree (3), Somewhat Agree (4), Agree (5) and Strongly Agree (6). The total score ranges from 23 to 138. The reliability co-efficient was found 0.85 and validity was found 51.91% using Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA).

2. Spiritual Values Scale

The Spiritual Values Scale (Husain A., Zehra S. and Jahan M., 2015) consisted of fifteen items with three dimensions i.e. Values Foster High Quality Work, Intrinsic Qualities and Natural Qualities. It is Likert type scale based on five points as Not at all Important (1), Not Important (2), Slightly Important (3), Important (4) and Very Important (5). The total score ranges from 15 to 75. The reliability co-efficient was found 0.887 and validity was found 51.91% using Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA).

3. Life Satisfaction Scale

Satisfaction with Life Scale (SWLS) The SWLS, which was developed by Diener, Emmons, Larsen, and Griffen (1985), contains five global items that were developed to assess an individual's satisfaction with life as a whole. The scale uses a 7-point Likert-type format that is as follows: strongly disagree (1), disagree (2), slightly disagree (3), neither agree nor disagree (4), slightly agree (5), agree (6), and strongly agree (7). The scores range from 5 to 35, the higher scores indicating more satisfaction with life. Hence, in terms of total scores, 5 to 9 indicates extremely dissatisfied with life, 10 to 14 indicates dissatisfied with life, 15 to 19 indicates slightly dissatisfied with life, 20 represents equally satisfied and dissatisfied with life, 21 to 25 indicates slightly satisfied, and 26 to 30 indicates satisfied with life, and 31 to 35 indicates extremely satisfied with life. Test-retest reliability and Cronbach's alpha were reported 0.82 and 0.87, respectively.

Procedure

The teachers were approached and asked to complete the questionnaires of Teacher's self efficacy, spiritual values and life satisfaction. All the respondents were also told that their anonymity will be preserved and their responses will be confidential. After that questionnaires were collected from the respondents and scored manually.

Statistical Analysis

In order to meet the research objectives data was analyzed; Pearson's product moment correlation was applied to study the relationship among teacher's self efficacy, spiritual

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values and life satisfaction. Further, Simple Linear Regression was administered to examine the influence of teacher's self efficacy and spiritual values on life satisfaction.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1: Shows Inter-correlation matrix (Self Efficacy, Spiritual Values and Life Satisfaction) N=120

Variables	Self Efficacy							Spiritual Values				Life Satisfaction	
	X1	X2	X3	X4	X5	X6	X7	X8	X9	X10	X11	Y1	
Self Efficacy	X1	1	.498**	.312**	.321**	.384**	.294**	.795**	.198*	.053	.085	.180*	.350**
	X2		1	.126	.371**	.389**	.207*	.785**	.240**	.346**	.101	.334**	.427**
	X3			1	.320**	.107	.242**	.419**	.008	.028	.009	.020	.046
	X4				1	.372**	.258**	.691**	.071	.190*	.173	.183*	.371**
	X5					1	.054	.597**	.026	.027	.142	.075	.223*
	X6						1	.408**	.097	.003	.033	.075	.216*
	X7							1	.203*	.218*	.152	.273**	.473**
Spiritual Values	X8							1	.154	.311**	.818**	.349**	
	X9								1	.268**	.605**	.195*	
	X10									1	.647**	.108	
	X11										1	.344**	
Life Satisfaction	Y1											1	

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

X1=Restraint, X2=Outgoing/Participating, X3=Evolving, X4= Versatile, X5=High Expectations, X6=Constructive, X7=Overall Self Efficacy, X8=Values Foster High Quality Work, X9= Intrinsic Qualities, X10=Natural Qualities, X11=Overall Spiritual Values, Y1=Overall Life Satisfaction.

Table 1 showed that overall self efficacy and its dimensions (i.e. Restraint, Outgoing/Participating, Evolving, Versatile, High Expectations and Constructive) were positively and significantly correlated with Life satisfaction. Therefore, H_{a1} is accepted as probability to accept the hypothesis was p<0.01 level of significance. Findings indicated that as the level of self efficacy of school teachers increases, their life satisfaction also increases. Thus, it can be inferred that school teachers who experienced higher level of self efficacy, expected to experience higher level of life satisfaction. A correlational study by Hampton (2000) also found that self efficacy and life satisfaction positively and significantly correlated

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with each other. Futher, Telef (2011) investigated the relationship between the self-efficacy, job satisfactions, life satisfactions and burnout of teachers. The sample consists of both male and female teachers. Results indicated that self-efficacy (efficacy for student’s engagement, efficacy for instructional strategies, and the efficacy for class management) had statistically significant positive relationship with teacher’s job and life satisfactions, and has a negative relationship with their burnout.

Table 1 showed that spiritual values and its dimension (i.e. Values Foster High Quality Work) were positively and significantly correlated with life satisfaction. Therefore, H₀₁ is accepted as probability to accept the hypothesis was $p < 0.01$ level of significance. Findings indicated that as the level of spiritual values of school teachers increases, their life satisfaction also increases. Thus, the results empirically confirmed that those school teachers who have higher level of spiritual values were found to have higher level of life satisfaction. It can be understood that when teachers having high spiritual values they have dedication to accomplish tasks and reach goals which confirms their high level of life satisfaction.

Table 2: Shows robustness checks for Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

Model	Predictors	R ²	Test of robustness					Whether robustness verified
			Linearity	Heteroscedasticity White Test (Range: $p < 0.05$)	Multicollinearity Tolerance & VIF (Range: Tol - 0-1, VIF- 1-9)	Normality PP Plots & Linearity Residual Plots	Independence Durbin – Watson (Range: DW<3)	
			1	2	3	4	5	
1	X ₁	.25	Satisfied	Satisfied	Tol : .824 VIF : 1.21	Satisfied	1.62	All Satisfied
2	X ₂	.22	Satisfied	Satisfied	Tol : 1.000 VIF : 1.000	Satisfied	1.55	

X_1 =Teacher’s Self Efficacy, X_2 =Spiritual Values, X_3 =Teacher’s Occupational Stress

It can be observed from the table 2 the robustness checks for linearity, Heteroscedasticity, multicollinearity, normality and independence satisfied.

Table 3: Shows Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

Predictors: Teacher’s Self-efficacy and Spiritual Values

Criterion: Life Satisfaction (Y₁)

Predictor Variables	Unstandardized β	Multiple R	R ²	Cohen’s f^2	F	p
Teacher’s Self Efficacy (TSE)	(Model $Y_1 = a + \beta_3 X_3$)					
X ₃	.82	0.50	0.25	0.08	33.95	0.001
Constant	1.495					

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Predictor Variables	Unstandardized β	Multiple R	R^2	Cohen's f^2	F	p
Spiritual Values (SV)	(Model $Y_1 = a + \beta_1 X_1$)					
X_8	0.56	0.35	0.12	0.14	16.35	0.001
<i>Constant</i>	10.10					
TSE & SV	(Model $Y_1 = a + \beta_7 X_7 + \beta_8 X_8$)					
X_7	0.21	0.47	0.22	0.28	71.55	0.001
X_8	0.42	0.54	0.29	0.09	24.05	0.001
<i>Constant</i>	10.57					

X_1 =Restraint, X_3 =Evolving, X_7 =Overall Self Efficacy, X_8 =Values Foster High Quality Work, Y_1 =Overall Life Satisfaction.

Stepwise method for selecting the predictor variables for the regression model was considered suitable, as it is probably the most commonly used method. If the variable fails to meet entry requirements (either FIN: F-to-enter or PIN: Probability of F-to-enter), the procedure terminates with no predictor variable in the equation. In stepwise method for fitting regression models the choice of predictive variables is carried and in each step, a variable is considered for addition to or subtraction from the set of explanatory variables based on some pre-specified criterion.

Further, the effect size for significant predictor variable was computed to estimate the magnitude or size of an effect on criterion variable. Cohen's f^2 is one of effect size measure was used in context of multiple regression analysis. Table 4.3 shows descriptors for magnitudes of f^2 as suggested by Cohen (1988). The formula used to calculate effect size (Cohen's f^2) is shown below:

$$f^2 = \frac{R^2}{1 - R^2}$$

Where R^2 is the squared multiple correlation

Table 4: Shows levels of effect-size

Effect Size	f^2
Small	0.02
Medium	0.15
Large	0.35

Whereas, self efficacy and its' dimensions were considered as predictors and life satisfaction as criterion to prepare a regression model. The Overall teacher's self efficacy accounted for a significant amount of variance in life satisfaction, $R^2=0.25$, $p < 0.001$. It can be inferred that overall teacher's self efficacy explaining 25% variance in life satisfaction of school teachers. Therefore, H_{a2} is supported. At the $\alpha = 0.001$ level of significance, there exists enough evidence to conclude that the slope of the population regression line is not zero and, hence, that teacher's self efficacy is useful predictor of life satisfaction of school teachers.

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Further, Cohen's effect size value ($f^2 = 0.08$) suggested a small to medium of association between teacher's self efficacy and life satisfaction.

Spiritual value was considered as predictor and life satisfaction as criterion to prepare a regression model. The Spiritual values accounted for a significant amount of variance in life satisfaction, $R^2=0.12$, $p < 0.001$. It can be inferred that Spiritual value explaining 12% variance in life satisfaction of school teachers. Therefore, H_{a2} is supported. At the $\alpha = 0.001$ level of significance, there exists enough evidence to conclude that the slope of the population regression line is not zero and, hence, that Spiritual value is useful predictor of life satisfaction for school teachers. Further, Cohen's effect size value ($f^2 = 0.14$) suggested a small to medium strength of association between Spiritual values and life satisfaction. A study conducted by Husain A., Zehra S. and Jahan M., (2015) in which they found that 'spiritual values of the employees are the fundamental roots of a healthy and vibrant organization. By exploring the employees' spiritual values, the integrated wholeness can bring forth tremendous strength in the work life, which leads them to life satisfaction.'

Teacher's self efficacy and Spiritual values were considered as predictors and life satisfaction as criterion to prepare a regression model. The self efficacy and Spiritual values accounted for a significant amount of variance in life satisfaction, $R^2=0.290$, $p < 0.001$. It can be inferred that self efficacy and spiritual values explaining 29% variance in life satisfaction of school teachers. Therefore, H_{a3} is partially supported. At the $\alpha = 0.001$ level of significance, there exists enough evidence to conclude that the slope of the population regression line is not zero and, hence, that Self-efficacy and spiritual values are useful predictors of life satisfaction for school teachers. Further, Cohen's effect size value ($f^2 = 0.09$) suggested a small to medium strength of association of self efficacy and spiritual values with life satisfaction. A number of studies were found in the same direction out of which Viel-Ruma et al. (2010) also studied teacher self efficacy, collective efficacy, and satisfaction in special educators, teachers in one school district completed three surveys measuring these constructs. The results indicated that teacher self efficacy had a direct effect on satisfaction.

CONCLUSION

Consequently, it is concluded that self efficacy and spiritual values are positively and significantly correlated with life satisfaction of school teachers. It is also concluded that self efficacy and spiritual values are having significant variance on life satisfaction of school teachers. It means that the people having greater level of spiritual values and self efficacy most probably experience better life satisfaction and vice versa. Because, people who have high level of self efficacy expected to tackle bad circumstances more conveniently as compare to low level of self efficacy. There is a general consensus that who accomplishes their works in time feel relaxes while others feel tense. On the same way those who experience higher level of spiritual values also expected to accomplish their work on time, because these values prompt an individual to do so. These all symptoms of dealing tendency are leading factors of life satisfaction. So that it may inferred that people are having high self efficacy, spiritual values may also have excellent level of life satisfaction.

Suggestion

The findings of study show a glimpse of the impact of teacher's self efficacy, spiritual values on life satisfaction among school teachers. However, more researches are needed to study the moderating factors of life satisfaction among different professions, culture as well as age groups. The findings of schools teachers could be compared with those found in other area of the world to decipher similarities and differences. As we know that teachers are nation builder so that there should be more effort to enhance their satisfaction level so that they can contribute in more beneficial way.

Acknowledgments

The author appreciates all those who participated in the study and helped to facilitate the research process.

Conflict of Interests: The author declared no conflict of interests.

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How to cite this article: Ansari M (2017). Self Efficacy and Spiritual Values as Predictors of Life Satisfaction among School Teachers. *International Journal of Indian Psychology*, Volume 4, (4), DIP:18.01.008/20170404, DOI:10.25215/0404.008